

Emerging Maximilian: temporal co-occurrences network analysis of people mentioned in Regesta Imperii XIII

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Introduction

We show here some early results of network analysis applications in the research project ManMax “Managing Maximilian: a prosopographical analysis on the Habsburg emperor Maximilian I (1459-1519)” [Research Project FWF SFB F9200 <https://managing-maximilian.net>]. Known as “the last Knight”, Maximilian is a key figure across two eras (Middle Age and Renaissance) who played a strategic role in European history since the political landscape drastically changed during and after his reign. The project, involving a large interdisciplinary team and different sources of data, aims to focus not only on Maximilian itself, often known as a skilled strategist and master of propaganda, but also on the role of many individuals and groups involved in those changes, inside and outside his court. While many data sources have been still digitizing, we focused here on Regesta Imperii XIII, which includes the documents issued by Maximilian's father and predecessor Frederick III (1415/1440-1493) and we propose a temporal analysis of co-occurrences networks that highlights the emerging role of Maximilian, leading the foundation for the rise of the House of Habsburg to become the most politically powerful dynasty in Europe in the following centuries.

Figure 1. Co-occurrence network of people mentioned in Regesta Imperii XIII. The more central nodes are colored in yellow and red (respectively denoting high values of degree and betweenness centrality). The main issue we want to focus on in this visualization is the role of time in the evolution of interactions, so we colored each edge according to the decade associated in the respective edge attribute "start_date", in order to highlight that such a large network is worth to be studied with a temporal perspective.

Dataset and Network Description

The Regesta Imperii (Rowan, 1973) is a large dataset that includes more than 150,000 abstracts of medieval charters issued by the Roman-German kings and popes distributed over many European locations and a time span of more than 700 years. We focused on the volume XIII, corresponding to the reign of Friedrich III, that has been completely digitized and labeled (Kuczera, 2019, Opitz et al., 2018, John et al., 2017), available at <https://gitlab.rlp.net/adwmainz/regesta-imperii/lab/regesta-imperii-data>.

In particular we selected the entities related to persons mentioned in the documents, and built a co-occurrence network (giant component) with more than 13K nodes and 230K edges, labeled with temporal and spatial information over a time interval of 53 years (1440-1493). Some people mentioned were actually dead in this time range, but often the death date is saved in the label so we easily drop these people out from our dataset. The network has been built as follows: if a person A and a person B appear in the same abstract we build an edge between nodes A and B, and we label this edge with the information related to that abstract (time and geographical info, if any). With a simple visualization obtained coloring the edges of the network according to their corresponding decade (see Figure 1), we can appreciate the crucial role of time in this network. This is a very huge dataset compared to the large majority of applications of network analysis in history and the large temporal span gives us the great opportunity to analyze in detail how the relationships evolved in time. To do this we then extracted the 53 sub-graphs induced by the date edge attributes, meaning that we consider the yearly network induced by relationships dated with a particular year, so for instance for 1483 we considered the co-occurrences of people mentioned in all the abstracts dated from 01-01-1483 to 12-31-1483. Dealing with those networks is certainly easier because they are smaller (usually less than 1000 nodes) and we will show in the following paragraphs how to use their local properties to have a global view of the whole dataset.

Figure 2. Temporal evolution of betweenness centrality in the network. Each (x,y) point represents the betweenness centrality rank (in the brokers top 10) of a person x in the year y. A red dot (x,y) in particular represents a high rank of person x in the brokers top 10 of year y, a blue dot means a lower rank. Notice that on the x axis are listed only the people who enter at some point in this "top 10", and we chose the number 10 to improve readability of "stories" in this plot. We highlight here for instance Maximilian, who increased his power in the last years of his father's reign, and Matthias Corvinus, the king of Hungary who was involved in war against Maximilian around 1483 and he gained influence in a short timeframe.

Temporal Centralities Results

Computing basic centrality measures (degree, betweenness) in the whole network we obtain a list of the most influential people in the full period covered by RI XIII. Since we are interested in how this influence was built, we split our large network into 53 independent sublayers corresponding to years from 1440 to 1493, as a multilayer temporal network (Kivela et al., 2014; Holme and Saramäki, 2019). For each layer we computed the centralities for all nodes (Prado, 2016) and then we considered those measures normalized

over the maximum value of that year, obtaining ranking values in $[0,1]$ that can be compared. The yearly lists of the first ten most influential individuals changes very quickly in time and are significantly different from the one of the whole network. Additionally, we can select one person and analyse the evolution of his power across time (see Figure 3). In order to visualize the global dynamics of influence over time we propose a visualization: a heatmap where we show, for each time step, the 10 nodes with highest centrality (Figure 2): a red dot in (x,y) represents a high rank for person x in the “brokers TOP10” (high betweenness) of year y , a blue dot means a lower rank in the same list. This temporal analysis of centralities shows some patterns that were completely hidden if we compute the same measures in the whole net. First of all, we can easily observe that the set of main actors changes quickly in time, and looking at columns and rows of the plot we are finding interesting stories. Maximilian, in the top-center of the plot, rapidly increases his power (a vertical sequence of red points) in the last years of his father's reign (Noflatscher, 1999; Wolf, 2005). Other persons otherwise have a high rank only in very short periods, which might link them to specific events dating in this period: this is the case of Matthias Corvinus, who was involved in a war around 1483 against Frederick III. Figure 3 shows a more detailed evolution of both measures for these two people, while Figure 4 is the visualization of the 1483 layer, a highly polarized network.

Figure 3. Evolution of normalized degree (lightblue) and betweenness (red) centrality over time for Maximilian (on the left) and Matthias Corvinus (on the right). We can notice here that there is a substantial coherence among the dynamics of both measures, but in some cases they are significantly different (for instance, high degree and low betweenness). These local properties could be explored more in detail to focus on individual roles of people in the prosopographical network.

Figure 4 Induced subgraph corresponding to the year 1483. The network appears to be highly polarized and we notice the central roles of the two main actors: Maximilian and Matthias Corvinus. They were indeed involved in a conflict and not surprisingly next to Matthias Corvinus we find the Ottomans and the Pope, who also had strategic roles on that period.

Temporal Communities Results

Similarly to centralities computation, running a community detection algorithm on the whole network we do not obtain interesting or meaningful results because of the very large size of the graph. Again, we decided to focus on individual layers, running a community detection locally: in Figure 4 the nodes are colored according to the Louvain algorithm. With this approach we obtain a reasonable number (10-15) of communities for each layer and we tried to exploit this local similarity to look for global patterns: we consider how many times two nodes appear in the same community and we build a new graph with this information, keeping only nodes (people) mentioned at least 3 years. Louvain's algorithm detected 7 communities in this new network, as represented in Figure 5: further discussion is needed here, but we already observed an overlapping among some communities and groups of people united by the same social function (1 - imperial elite, 2 - nobility, 3-6 functionaries etc) or by the same geographical areas (4,5,7).

Figure 5 For each yearly projection we ran the Louvain community detection algorithm and then we built a network in which each link (i,j) weighted with w represents people i and j that appear in the same community for w years. Here is the result of the Louvain algorithm on this network: 7 communities that we label with a preliminary qualitative analysis.

Conclusions

The results of a temporal analysis are encouraging and we are still exploring them in order to better understand power relationships during Frederick III's reign (Heinig, 1997), especially in the last years, where the role of Maximilian started to be crucial. For instance, we would like to study in detail the structure of the sublayers to explore eventual correlations among the network topology and some specific periods in the timeline, such as wars.

About the focus topic of this event (visualization), we experimented here several types of network visualizations that highlight the role of time: coloring edges according to their decade, or focusing only on yearly sublayers. Moreover, we think that the heatmap representation of the measures across time is a very informative tool, even if not a direct network visualization, that immediately gives an idea of most influential nodes in different years, specially for large temporal graphs.

On the other hand, we want to stress the main limitation of dealing with co-occurrences networks: considering mentions that appear in the same short text, the real nature of the interactions (if there is any) is totally ignored. This can lead to misinterpretation and overrepresentation problems. Instead, a more consistent and coherent representation could be done considering the semantics of the text that describes

the relationship, or considering a manually assigned ontology of relationships in a structured dataset (payments, communications, commissions etc.). We are currently working in building a prosopographical network based on both approaches in order to combine these two perspectives: extracting multilayer networks representing different types of relationships (Padgett-Ansell, 1993) and temporal network analysis on these layers. When feasible, we would also like to represent the social network with a signed graph, labeling the interactions as positive or negative, and to compute how the balance evolves in time.

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The codes and other material can be found here:
<https://github.com/GVogeler/ManMax-RIFIII>